

Digital fashion ideology: towards a critical public sphere

YeSeung Lee

University of Westminster

- The Version of Record of this manuscript has been published by SAGE and is available in *International Journal of Cultural Studies* (24 June 2025).
- To cite this article: Lee, YeSeung (2025) Digital fashion ideology: towards a critical public sphere. *International Journal of Cultural Studies*, 29 (1): 75–99.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/13678779251351644>.

ABSTRACT

Digital fashion communities are often portrayed as radical challengers to mainstream fashion, embodying digital utopianism that views technology as a liberating force. These communities are believed to reject industry hierarchies and adopt a countercultural stance. This study examines whether they truly embody such revolutionary ideals by analysing evidence gathered through an AI social listening platform. Despite the ambitious rhetoric, the findings show that online conversations within digital fashion often lack depth, relying on superficial slogans. The attitudes lack transformative resolve, reinforcing established industry hierarchies. This suggests digital fashion spaces have yet to function as meaningful public spheres, with commercial interests prevailing. This study, therefore, emphasises the importance of continuing education to develop critical thinking, as the discourse around digital fashion requires neither blind optimism nor pessimism, but rather careful deliberation of emerging practices and institutions at the physical-digital intersection.

KEYWORDS digital fashion, digital utopianism, artificial intelligence, social listening, public sphere, critical thinking

INTRODUCTION

The field of digital fashion is rapidly changing, with emerging technologies and concepts resulting in inconsistent terminology. As the field develops, it is expected that terminology will become more precise and standardised. The term 'digital fashion' is commonly used but difficult to define. The review of its usage on social media in this study suggests that the term encompasses a broad range of meanings. These include virtual garments designed for avatars in extended reality (XR) and their physical counterparts;¹ and the virtual production of physical clothing using digital tools such as smart mirrors and CLO3D software. The term also covers digital manufacturing processes (3D printing, digital printing, and laser cutting, for example). Some definitions include any online fashion presentation—portfolios, exhibitions, or events. The term 'metaverse' also exemplifies the terminological ambiguity, often being mistakenly conflated with digital fashion. While Dionisio et al. (2013: 6-7) define it as 'a fully immersive three-dimensional digital environment' that evolved from 'an amplified version of an individual virtual world' to 'a large network of interconnected virtual worlds',² the fashion industry uses the term more loosely.³

This paper adopts the narrower definition of digital fashion: virtual garments in XR and their physical counterparts, avoiding the term metaverse.⁴ In this specific context, digital fashion items are often traded in online marketplaces via so-called Web3 technologies.⁵ Like Web3 advocates questioning the established centralised structure of the internet, digital fashion communities are considered radical for their critiques of the mainstream fashion: they are perceived to reject industry hierarchies and link fashion choices to broader sociopolitical ideals.⁶ For example, The Fabricant (2022), a digital fashion company, champions this perspective on the blogging platform *Medium*: 'Web3 is the new punk. ... A decentralised and permissionless internet powered by blockchain, that places community and identity front and centre.' In a different blog advocating the use of generative AI, they contend that digital fashion allows designers to create new aesthetics 'without any physical waste' and is 'democratising access to the world of fashion' (The Fabricant 2024). Similar rhetoric appears in a blog by the Metaverse Fashion Council (2024):

DAFAC (Decentralised Autonomous Fashion Couturier) is an AI agent ... its mission [is] to disrupt traditional systems and build a future where transparency, traceability, and innovation are the norm. ... [Its] creations are inherently sustainable: 3D-printed on-demand, with no waste, no labor exploitation, and infinite recyclability.

However, these idealistic perspectives are not universally accepted. For instance, Karinna Grant of The Dematerialised—a digital fashion platform—notes that many buyers are primarily 'looking to make a quick buck' (Heneage 2023). Despite ambitious rhetoric, much of the engagement with digital fashion may lack substantial commitment to its stated transformative visions.

Nevertheless, these expressions shed light on current concerns and aspirations within the fashion industry and its public. Although evidence of sustained critical engagement is limited, I use the term 'public' to emphasise active stakeholder participation through discourse and practice that extend beyond commercial transactions. It may evoke Jürgen Habermas's ([1962] 1991) idea of the 'public sphere', referring to spaces of communication where people deliberate on collective issues to seek democratically legitimate solutions (Pfister 2018). Habermas argued that such space declined with the rise of mass media, where open and critical debate was replaced by passive consumption of culture (Livingstone and Lunt 1994). The concept of the 'fashion public' can help examine digital fashion as a potential space for sociopolitical deliberation that transcends commercialised content and performative activism. While digital spaces may foster critical fashion dialogue, they also risk exacerbating mindless consumption and reinforcing the passivity Habermas associated with mass media. What is the future of fashion in societies that increasingly rely on algorithms for decision-making? How might fashion practices evolve as profit-driven technology companies shape corporate and consumer behaviour?

I have previously examined the viability of the fashion public by drawing potential parallels between activated spectatorship in fine/performance art and fashion presentations—exploring whether broader access to fashion shows through digital media can enable critical engagement with sociopolitical issues

(Lee 2024). Building on this, this study probes whether the popular portrayal of current digital fashion communities as radical—using technology as a force for decentralisation, sustainable development, or enhanced accountability—aligns with social media gathered through an AI social listening platform. The findings suggest that social media discourse around digital fashion frequently lacks depth, relying on superficial slogans and buzzwords. The prevalent attitude is more inquisitive than revolutionary, with most content reinforcing existing fashion hierarchies and preserving core exclusionary frameworks. This study calls for a critical reassessment of the perceived radicalism of digital fashion communities and emphasises the importance of genuine debate and education.

The article first examines the ideological and technical premise of digital fashion's purported radicalism, identifying historical and contemporary digital utopianisms and participatory approaches within the network of art, design, and media as key influences. It further examines how the early digital utopianisms evolved alongside internet technologies, revealing the chasm between digital fashion's aspiration and reality. The second section investigates how Web3 technologies and values influence digital fashion ideology, focusing on three key aspects—environmental sustainability, decentralisation, and digital accountability via transparency, security, and privacy—along with associated challenges and opportunities. The final section details the AI social listening methodology, processes, findings, and analyses, and addresses the methodological constraints. The conclusion highlights the shortcomings of digital fashion spaces in functioning as a meaningful public sphere, proposing thoughtful deliberation and continuing education.

IDEOLOGICAL and TECHNICAL INFLUENCES

Digital utopianisms and Web1

Digital fashion's supposed anti-establishment stance reflects 'digital utopianism', a recurring idealism that believes 'new technology will bring universal wealth, enhanced freedom, revitalised politics, satisfying community, and personal fulfillment' (Winner 1997a: 1001).⁷ Web3 builds on these premises by combining the infrastructure of Web1 with the social aspects of Web2 (Hawes

2023: 11). A brief outline of historical digital utopianisms would be valuable here for understanding how contemporary digital fashion superficially co-opts their rhetoric through Web3 discourse.

The pioneering phase of electronic computing started in the 1940s in the UK, the US, and Germany focusing on wartime military needs, before its development expanded more widely to other countries in the 1950s. While these early efforts were driven by government-funded military-industrial-academic initiatives (Rosen 1969; Turner 2006a: 15, 17-18; 2023a), the research environments nurtured distributed and interdisciplinary collaboration (Buderi 1996: 129-130; Waldrop 2001. Turner 2006a: 19). Norbert Wiener (1948)—associated with the MIT Radiation Laboratory during World War II—argued that cybernetics could create more egalitarian power structures, challenging the dominance of corporations, governments, and authoritarian systems (Waldrop 2001: Ch3; Turner 2023b). Cybernetics was embraced by the countercultural communities of the 1960s-70s, particularly in and around the San Francisco Bay Area, where it played an important role in the development of the personal computer and its conception as a tool of political and personal rebellion (Turner 2006b: 259-260). The Californian Ideology combined this optimistic belief in digital technology's emancipatory power with the ethos counterculture (Barbrook and Cameron 1995). In particular, the groups that Fred Turner (2013: 44) refers to as 'New Communalists' opposed mass consumerism and state/corporate control of technological resources, advocating that people should develop skills to reclaim technology for creative and social uses (Turner 2013: 44).⁸ It should be noted, however, that the vast majority of New Communalists were young, well-educated, middle- and upper-class white Americans, who often disregarded issues of gender, racial, social, or class equity (Turner 2013: 46-47). This chasm between the movement's idealistic vision and the overlooked inequalities endures in contemporary digital utopianism, where the pursuit of innovation frequently sidesteps meaningful engagement with its social and ecological costs.

Wiener's cybernetic theories also helped to reframe fine art beyond the binary of active production and passive consumption toward interactive feedback systems (Mason 2018). In Britain, 'computer art'⁹ thrived under the

Labour government's (1964-1970) support of technology as key drivers of economic prosperity (Wilson 1963), in addition to grassroots efforts to broaden access to technology, away from military-industrial control. Two landmark exhibitions in 1968 crystallised this vision: 'Cybernetic Serendipity' (Institute of Contemporary Arts, London), curated by Jasia Reichardt, presented technology and art, scientists and artists, as well as machines and artworks on an equal footing. In Zagreb, the New Tendencies movement presented 'Tendencies 4', addressing technology's dual potential for control and liberation while promoting accessible art (Mason 2018).

The personal computing revolution of the 1980s—the Apple Lisa (1983), the Microsoft Windows (1983), the Apple Macintosh (1984)—was heavily influenced by countercultural ideals, with the figure of the 'hippie-hacker' emerging as a symbol that bridged the worlds of computing and utopian counterculture (Turner 2006b: 259, 263, 265). The personalisation of computers also brought Graphical User Interfaces (GUIs), marking a shift toward visual computing that shapes how humans interact with digital tools today. It is also notable that cinema began visualising the digital realm via computer-generated effects during this period—Steven Lisberger's *TRON* (1982), for instance, featured a distinctive visual style and a hippie-hacker protagonist who embodied techno-utopian ideals (Rose 2022).¹⁰

When the Internet and the World Wide Web became publicly accessible in the mid-1990s, cyberspace embodied egalitarian ideals that challenged corporate power (Turner 2006a: 13; 2006b: 257). The first generation of the Internet, Web1 (1990-2004), consisted primarily of static, read-only pages like blogs and message boards. It is often said that Web1 enabled decentralised and non-hierarchical information sharing. In practice, building a website and participating as a creator required technical skills, while limited search functionality meant finding relevant information also posed challenges for users (Hawes 2023: 9). Technology researcher Ben Hawes (2023: 10) argues that same technical challenge remains a crucial factor in wider Web3 adoption, raising doubts about equity in digital fashion.

Web2: promise and reality

The arrival of Web2 in the early 2000s marked a major shift towards a more participatory internet. This shift was enabled by platforms that allowed users to easily create and share content, facilitating co-creation (Orton-Johnson 2024: CH5). The resulting rise of digital prosumption—where consumers also become producers of goods and services—challenged traditional amateur-expert hierarchy (Toffler 1980; Ritzer and Jurgenson 2010; Beer and Burrows 2010) via open participation and peer validation, echoing earlier countercultural movements aimed at making skills and tools accessible for creative and social uses. This shift aligns with the emergence of the 'creator economy', a system where individuals earn income through digital content creation (Peres et al. 2024; Karp et al. 2024). Social media platforms accelerated this transformation: in fashion, visual-focused platforms—especially Instagram—have become a key space for emerging creators to publish their work, lowering barriers to entry and generating opportunities for collaboration (See section 'Content distribution across platforms' below).

Web2's social interactivity and participatory nature were complemented by the evolution of 3D content creation and gaming platforms during the early 2000s. The popular 3D graphics software Blender went open source in 2002, allowing user-driven development. Simulated everyday worlds like *The Sims* (2000) allow gamers to customise their in-game environment and character skins (Watstein and Czarnecki 2010: 276-277) while user contributions shape entire digital environments in *Second Life* (2003) (Dionisio et al. 2013). *Roblox* (2006) enables users to create, share, and monetise their own games. User-friendly 3D graphic software such as Clo Marvelous Designer (2009) and CLO3D (2010) enables users to design and share sophisticated digital assets. Software expert Eric S. Raymond's (1999) metaphor 'cathedral and bazaar'—contrasting closed, hierarchical systems (the cathedral model) with open, distributed networks (the bazaar model)—prefigured this shift toward more open systems of creation. In fashion, The Fabricant operates through a 'network of freelancers', embracing a 'co-creational open-source philosophy' that includes sharing digital garments and streaming tutorials (Särmäkari and Vänskä 2022: 215, 218). Traditional fashion studios can learn from open-source communities and digital game studios, particularly their cultures of cross-disciplinary

collaboration and knowledge sharing (Black 2019: 124; Tepe and Koohnavard 2022: 38).

The creative and/or civic participation of the 'platformed masses' (Lovink and Tkacz 2015: 14; Langley and Leyshon 2017: 17) has thus significantly challenged traditional media, creative industries, and information flows. The open-source movement and user-generated content platforms seemed to fulfil early internet pioneers' dreams of a democratic digital commons. Indeed, digital utopianism has even given birth to new political movements and governance models; for example, Italy's Movimento Cinque Stelle (founded in 2009) envisioned implementing web-based direct democracy, seeing 'the web as the catalyst of revolutionary change' (Natale and Ballatore 2014: 112, 114, 118).

In terms of consumption, Web2 amplified the formation and cohesion of internet-enabled communities of choice, where geographically dispersed individuals are 'connected by shared lifestyles, interests, beliefs, institutions, goals or values' (Orton-Johnson 2024; See also Castells 2001: 125). Niche market consumers often form such online communities, approaching dominant corporate entities with scepticism (Karp et al. 2024). This sentiment appears to echo the countercultural values of Californian Utopianism, and the perceived attitude of digital fashion communities toward mainstream fashion can also be analysed within this context.

The vision of a community-driven society has faced significant challenges since the late 2000s. First revealed are the fundamental flaws in its participatory premise. Despite the persistent myth of egalitarian online interactivity, only a small percentage of individuals engage actively in participatory ways. (van Dijck and Nieborg 2009; Orton-Johnson 2024) In addition, the absence of gatekeeping, combined with mass individual content publishing, often leads to a chaotic environment where constructive discourse struggles to emerge. This cacophony of unmediated voices ultimately challenges the very social cohesion that the Californian Ideology had aspired to build (Turner 2023a). As Henry Jenkins (2014: 284) suggests, online participatory practices 'do not necessarily inculcate democratic values or develop shared ethical norms, do not necessarily respect and value diversity'. Indeed, social

trust is eroding as dis-/mal-information and other fraudulent content proliferate.¹¹

This weakening of social fabric is one of the consequences of 'platform capitalism' (Srnicsek 2017; Langley and Leyshon 2017: 17). Undermining the ideals of Web2, major platforms have become powerful intermediaries controlling digital interactions and human attention. Their monopolistic control operates alongside 'surveillance capitalism', where platforms systematically accumulate, codify, and marketise user data as their primary revenue source (Foster and McChesney 2014; Zuboff 2015; Langley and Leyshon 2017: 23). In consequence, platforms and their 'attention economy' privilege sensational and emotional content over what is measured and nuanced. Receiving social affirmation through 'like' buttons conditions users into seeking validation through curated content while facilitating social platforms to harvest and monetise user data. Engineered to maximise attention, online conversations frequently come at the expense of rational deliberation. This reveals the fragility of the online public sphere, where politics are more a product of algorithmic influence rather than reflecting human deliberation (Pfister and Yang 2018: 252).

In addition, Web2 platforms' surveillance capabilities have been used for anti-democratic purposes (Reed 2018: 125, 127; The Economist 2024). For example, the 2018 Cambridge Analytica scandal revealed how personal data like clothing preferences can also be used to construct detailed voter profiles without consent (Friedman and Bromwich 2018). Chinese Communist Party's censorship covers social media content deemed 'anti-China'¹² and generative AI models like DeepSeek, which are programmed to avoid challenging CCP's 'core socialist values' (Lu 2025). Such control mechanisms have broader geopolitical implications (Rolf and Schindler 2023: 1255). For instance, AI-generated fashion models or virtual influencers on social platforms like TikTok and RedNote engage with audiences in ways that blur the line between reality and virtual. Despite appearing frivolous and apolitical, these influencers shape Taiwanese perceptions of China, raising concerns about a 'cultural unification war' (Wu 2024). Fashion and beauty content consistently receives the highest engagement on social media (Highhouse 2022: 709; Wu 2024), making it an

effective tool for China's soft power strategy to reach 'into the island, into the household, into the brain, into the heart' (Graham-Harrison and Lin 2023). Exposure to subtly manipulated content can shape perceptions over time, leading some to view China in a more positive light, potentially reducing resistance to Beijing's broader political aims (Bonsaver 2025; Highhouse 2022: 697; Hille 2025), while reinforcing narratives that suppress Taiwanese identity (Richardson 2025).

Digital surveillance and privacy concerns intensify as fashion increasingly merges with gaming and XR environments. VR headsets that track eye movements and AR applications that map private spaces exemplify how this 'dataveillance'¹³ raises risks of potential breaches and unauthorised access to personal information (Hadi et al. 2024: 158; Pfister and Yang 2018: 256). These challenges highlight the urgent need for both regulatory frameworks and robust civic education to equip the public with critical thinking skills.

Dematerialisation of fashion, internet culture, and user agency

As stated in the introduction, this study focuses on digital fashion within extended reality environments. Garments in extended realities can blur the boundaries between body and environment, allowing them to exist as fluid interfaces. For example, gaming's immersive environments—combining visuals, sound, and interactivity—offer a unique opportunity for experiments, aligning well with digital fashion's trajectory. This shared emphasis appears to drive the gaming-digital fashion convergence: in 2023, CLO Virtual Fashion and Epic Games purchased shares in each other to enhance interoperability across their products (CLO Virtual Fashion 2023; Bain 2023). As the gaming revenue exceeds that of film and music combined (Moore 2024), large fashion brands are establishing presences on gaming platforms as well as in esports events (Leroux-Parra 2020). However, this trend risks consolidating power within established brands, undermining the ideals of a decentralised creator economy rooted in equity and distribution. For 'advergaming'—*LOUIS: The Game* (Louis Vuitton, 2019) and *Afterworld* (Balenciaga, 2020), for example—brands create bespoke gaming experiences rather than simply inserting their products into existing games (Terlutter and Capella 2013). While these examples highlight

fashion's potential in immersive spaces, they also reveal how the convergence can reinforce the existing hierarchy, with major brands maintaining control over digital assets and experiences. Concepts like 'playbour'—the blurring of lines between play and work in the gaming industry—exemplifies how user agency is challenged (Kücklich 2005): players often generate significant value to platforms by creating and customising fashion digital assets without receiving economic benefits or copyright recognition. According to social media discussions, Web3 gaming aims to address these issues through tokenisation and digital ownership. However, this remains largely theoretical, leaving important questions about labour and value creation in virtual spaces unresolved.

As regards consumption, one aspect of dematerialisation is that it intensifies the mediatisation of the self, creating more opportunities for the self to be represented and shared through digital channels. For example, as 'social surveillance' (Marwick 2012)—mutual peer monitoring—is a common aspect of social media use, users curate their digital presence to reflect desired identities, which can influence their sense of self in return, contributing to identity formation. On one hand, this process can nurture creative self-expression and protect marginalised individuals through anonymity. On the other hand, it may also contribute to increasingly troubling issues surrounding self-image: AI-powered social media filters have been widely criticised for distorting self-perception, with cases where individuals seek surgical alterations to resemble their filtered images exemplifying such issues (Pescott 2023). Generative AI tools are further complicating the situation, often perpetuating biases embedded in training data that favour certain facial features and body types (Scott and Armstrong 2024). While platforms like Meta offer extensive avatar customisation (Hadi et al. 2024: 158-159) virtual identity representation remains problematic.¹⁴ Moreover, deepfakes and other readily available digital manipulation technologies blur the lines of authenticity, exacerbating distrust (U.S. Copyright Office 2024; Nguyen and Workman 2024) and raising concerns about the unchecked powers of the tool-enabled individual (Turner 2013: 43).

Critical attention should be given to the mediatisation of self within virtual environments, as avatar culture increasingly permeates everyday life through e-meetings and other online activities, heightening the demand for

sophisticated digital assets. A 2023 Roblox survey found that 56% of Gen Z gamers prioritise their avatar's styling over their physical appearance, highlighting the significance of virtual self-presentation (Wootton and Bronstein 2023). The same survey shows that avatars impact even offline identities, with 84% of Gen Z gamers reporting their real-world style is influenced by their avatar's appearance (ibid.). While these statistics emerge from gaming platforms, they may signal broader behavioural patterns as customising avatars become more important for everyday online interactions.

DIGITAL FASHION IDEOLOGY and WEB3

Based on insights from the social listening platform, digital fashion's ability to transcend physical boundaries has yet to fully realise its sociopolitical potential. Advocates of Web3 argue that its technologies could unlock this potential. Web3 itself emerged as a response to the shortcomings of Web2, aiming to address issues related to the erosion of liberal values. However, it represents the latest iteration of digital utopianism, equally facing tensions between aspirations and practical constraints. The highly polarised discourse surrounding Web3 reflects broader questions about how digital technologies can better serve society. It also informs critical debates around digital fashion, which tend to incorporate Web3 discourse with limited critique. The following three themes represent the most frequently debated topics, along with their respective challenges and opportunities.

Decentralisation

Web3 uses blockchain technology to build applications where users, rather than large institutions, retain control over their data. While this idea has gained traction in digital fashion, its benefits are often overstated, as is the case with the general perception of Web3 (Stackpole 2022; Hawes 2023: 5). On the production side, the adoption of Web3 in digital fashion is often seen as a move toward decentralised creation and collaboration, shifting from Web2's 'cathedral'—with its associated issues of platform capitalism, surveillance capitalism, and digital colonialism—to a user-controlled 'bazaar'. In practice, most creators still rely on centralised marketplaces that charge fees, as they lack

the technical and/or financial means to operate independently. As such, the vision of Web3 creator autonomy remains largely theoretical (Stackpole 2022; Hawes 2023: 24). Moreover, blockchain systems face operational challenges, often slowing during peak periods (Stackpole 2022), which leads to centralised administration to maintain stability. Many NFT marketplaces and blockchain platforms are emerging as powerful intermediaries, often replicating Web2 power dynamics and concentrating influence among those with early access and technical abilities (Hawes 2023: 7, 23). In addition, the lack of governance and clear regulation means problems cannot be rectified efficiently (Murray et al. 2023).

On the consumption side, digital fashion presentations have made some luxury experiences more accessible. However, Web3 digital products can create new barriers, with luxury NFTs and limited-edition virtual items generating artificial scarcity and exclusivity (TFL 2022).¹⁵ More importantly, the global and local digital divide persists: many people still lack the basic technology needed to participate, as reliable internet and devices remain out of reach (Orton-Johnson 2024). Overall, the issue of equitable power and distribution remains uncertain, as the benefits often go to those with early access, rather than society as a whole (Winner 1997b: 16; Murray et al. 2023).

Environmental sustainability

A widely held view of digital fashion is that it is a more sustainable production and consumption model by minimising material waste. However, statements like 'the digital space is inherently more sustainable—no physical materials, no waste, just pure creativity' (Antoni Tudisco cited in Tan 2024) and The Fabricant's (2024) assertion of creating 'without any physical waste' are overly simplistic, as they overlook the substantial energy consumption of digital infrastructure—server farms, cloud computing, and digital devices. The Proof-of-Work blockchain model also requires vast computing power.¹⁶ Therefore, marketing digital fashion as 'zero waste' amounts to greenwashing when it merely shifts consumption from fabrics to electricity and rare earth materials rather than reducing resource use. In addition, virtual-only fashion may

normalise disposable consumption habits and accelerate trend cycles, potentially encouraging a throwaway mindset that extends to physical fashion.

Transparency, privacy, and security

Web3's decentralised infrastructure may provide users more transparent and immutable transaction records. Through NFTs, creators can establish authentic ownership and protect their intellectual property, whilst users can verify supply chain integrity and detect counterfeit goods. However, there exist inherent tensions between blockchain's transparency, permanence, and immutability against fundamental privacy rights (Blackman 2022). Blockchain's immutability clashes with privacy regulations like GDPR's 'Right to be forgotten' (Stackpole 2022; Blackman 2022), and the permanent nature of blockchain records means abusive or sensitive materials cannot be removed (Stackpole 2022; U.S. Copyright Office 2025). The most pressing challenge, perhaps, lies in consumer awareness: a 2024 YouGov poll shows that 42% of Americans aged 18-34 are unconcerned about online data privacy, compared to 24% of over-55s. Deloitte's 2024 poll indicates that two-thirds of Gen Z and millennial consumers in America believe online service benefits outweigh data privacy concerns (The Economist 2025).

Digital fashion ideology's blind faith in Web3 technology overlooks the highly critical views on its scalability and risks (Hawes 2023: 5, 19). In the social media content collected through the Pulsar platform, the three key debates were present but only to a very minimal degree, as detailed in the following section.

AI SOCIAL LISTENING

Methodology and ethics

This study used real-time and historical data gathered via Pulsar, an AI-powered social listening platform. Social listening—the systematic gathering and analysis of social media content—provided insights into the behaviours of digital fashion communities through their voluntarily shared interactions on social platforms. Social listening demands robust privacy protocols when

analysing online interactions, given increasingly blurred lines boundaries between public and private data (Kozinets 2022). This study followed the guidelines proposed by Townsend and Wallace (2016), staying up to date with social media platforms' terms of service, using Pulsar which meets regulatory requirements (Palmer 2024), and following British Academy's (2024) award requirements. Social media users consent to data sharing through terms of service, and sharing aggregate data in social media research is generally considered safe, as individuals can no longer be identified (Townsend and Wallace 2016: 13).

For this study, the Pulsar platform collected and processed digital content over a period of eight months (10 March-19 November 2024). After regular filtering, 88,141 posts were compiled from nine social media platforms (Instagram, X, YouTube, Facebook, TikTok, Reddit, Pinterest, Twitch, and Threads) and open-access online news sites, blogs, and forums to better match user-generated social media content. This approach of collecting, analysing, and interpreting online traces aligns with frameworks such as 'digital ethnography', 'cyberethnography', 'netnography', or 'virtual ethnography' (Orton-Johnson 2024: CH2).

Main search: 'Digital fashion'

The initial data collection started on 10 March 2024 using keywords drawn from The Fabricant's blogs (<https://thefabricant.medium.com/>), including 'virtual fashion', 'metaverse', 'decentralised', 'collaborative', 'transparency', and 'subcultures'. When the search did not yield sufficiently relevant results, the parameters were expanded to 'digital fashion' on 19 March 2024.¹⁷ The search was limited to the English term to avoid inconsistencies from machine translation and cross-linguistic variations. Using a single language also facilitated the elimination of 'noise' (irrelevant content and spam) while refining search terms to minimise dataset contamination. The 2.8% non-English content collected—due to the popularity of #digitalfashion—was translated via Claude AI and Google Translate. The broader search parameter significantly complicated data refinement. It also increasingly became clear that Pulsar's AI reports lacked analytical depth.

Upon data saturation with no new patterns emerging (10 November 2024), Pulsar's AI tools identified dominant narratives and keywords. These initial analytics revealed limited evidence of socio-politically conscious audience. For example, the analysis of author biography keywords (Figures 1) reveals that sociopolitical foci constitute only a small fraction of the overall focus. Author biographies typically consist of self-selected information that reflects the authors' current or aspirational identities and may provide more reliable data for analysis than the keywords found in post content. From the author biography keywords collected, 'decentralised', 'ambassador', 'web3', 'blockchain', 'NFT', 'future', and 'access' were identified as potentially indicating a degree of sociopolitical consciousness (Figure 2). More general words—'digital', 'art', 'fashion', 'projects', 'design', 'technology', 'fusion', 'artist', 'canvas', 'exciting', 'diving', 'discover', 'unique', 'tech'—were disregarded for efficiency. It should be noted that the presence of the select keywords does not necessarily indicate genuine sociopolitical awareness, as they could simply reflect an interest in financial investments, for instance. The limitations of keyword-based content analysis are discussed further in the conclusion.

Fig. 1. Author biography keywords analysis (19 Mar–10 November 2024). Sociopolitical foci (volume 4383. 4.8%) in comparison with other foci (volume 86705. 95.2%)

Fig. 2. Distribution of author biography keywords (19 Mar–10 November 2024). The word 'web3' appeared 1,528 times, 'NFT' (1,375), 'blockchain' (759), 'future' (628), 'ambassador' (364), 'decentralised' (23), 'access' (13)

Supplementary search

Since the first search was insufficient to address the research question, a supplementary search—'digital fashion and sociopolitical consciousness'—was introduced (28 June–10 November 2024). This search incorporated Pulsar's AI-suggested keywords to identify potential indicators of progressive tendencies.¹⁸

To compare author demographics across the two searches, the main search collected 43,526 posts from 21,000 unique authors (95%), while supplementary search yielded 1,424 posts from 1,100 authors (5%) (Figure 3).

Fig. 3. Unique authors (28 June–10 November 2024). 'Digital fashion': 21,000 (95%); 'DFSC': 1,100 (5%)

Fig. 4. Associations by keywords: the five main narratives in 'DFSC' search (28 June–10 November 2024)

Pulsar's analytics identified the main narratives within the supplementary search (Figure 4). The AI analysis of the narrative with the highest number of contributing authors (322) reads: 'The metaverse is increasingly being viewed as a lucrative opportunity for passive income and brand establishment. ... Backed by notable partnerships and celebrity endorsements, these platforms are gaining credibility and momentum, with users able to create and monetise their own experiences.' The related posts appear more focused on commercial rather than societal interests such as equitable systems, ethical practices, data security, and sustainability. The AI analysis for the 'collaboration, launches' narrative (207 unique authors) was most relevant to the research question: 'There's a notable shift towards digital fashion, NFT collaborations, and eco-friendly practices' in the fashion industry.!

Manual monitoring (main search)

The analysis of commercial interest above provided useful insights, but the AI-generated texts mostly offered surface-level summaries. Therefore, 'digital fashion' search posts were manually filtered and evaluated for 38 days (04 October–10 November 2024). While this intervention—along with the selection of the author biography keywords above—inevitably introduced researcher subjectivity, it aligns with Orton-Johnson's (2024) observation that all data is

inherently socially constructed and filtered through researchers' efforts to understand phenomena.

In manually evaluating posts for sociopolitical awareness, an inclusive approach was taken. That is, all posts with relevant keywords were considered, even those clearly lacking depth or detail. This meant the dataset included much superficial content that may not reflect genuine intentions. Still, the number of relevant posts remained extremely low (Figures 5).

Fig. 5. Distribution of posts in 'digital fashion' search (4 October–10 November 2024)

Figure 6 shows the main themes identified in the 79 posts that display varying levels of sociopolitical awareness. The most frequently mentioned opportunities centre on equity in production and in consumption, environmental sustainability, and transparency. The posts seldom address challenges, which suggests a limited awareness or a biased perspective. Most social media posts—particularly portfolios and platform/marketplace advertisements—lack detail, context, or concrete examples, relying heavily on popular keywords and well-rehearsed slogans. The lack of depth is matched by many blogs and online articles, which often appear to be AI-generated, regurgitating similar content (see Knibbs 2024, Vincent 2023).

OPPORTUNITIES	Equity in production (wider access to creative tools and opportunities; collaboration and sharing)	32
	Equity in consumption (catering to diverse cultural/ economic/ racial/ ethnic backgrounds, body types, genders, ages, and disabilities)	32
	Environmental sustainability	31
	Transparency (IP/ counterfeit, supply chain, ownership)	14
	Campaign (advocacy, manifesto)	7
	Sustainability (no detail)	6
	Cultural sustainability	3
	Democratisation (no detail)	1
	Data privacy	1
	Decentralisation	1
CHALLENGES	Job insecurity (AI automation)	3
	Digital inequity	3
	Data exposure and privacy concerns	2
	Environmental damage	2
	Inequality in consumption	2
	Distrust (dis/misinformation, AI influencers, 'deepfakes')	1
	Social isolation, health issues, addiction	1
	Consumer education	1

Fig. 6. Sociopolitical themes in digital fashion on social media: opportunities and challenges.

Noteworthy exceptions include an *ABC News* article (Nguyen and Workman 2024) addressing the challenges posed by generative AI in fashion, including intellectual property concerns, job security risks, algorithmic bias that can perpetuate existing societal inequalities. The article also addressed the pressing need for robust regulatory frameworks to govern AI's development and implementation. A data analytics company's post on X also emphasised legislative efforts to combat algorithm-driven fast fashion trends perpetuating waste. A few refreshing collaborative moments stood out, including a game developer sharing open-source digital fashion tools and works-in-progress, embodying Web3's participatory design ethos.

Fig. 7. Content distribution: 'digital fashion' search posts by platform (1–10 Nov 2024)

Content distribution across platforms

As a final step, to gain a more in-depth understanding of the content shared across platforms, individual posts were manually tagged and categorised (1–10 November 2024). Nine categories emerged in the process (Figure 7): portfolio (579 posts), skill-share/freelancing offer (128), promotion (events/organisation) (95), education (tutorials/courses) (71), Web3 (64), designer/influencer (42), sociopolitical consciousness (32), XR/gaming (18), and research (3). Despite taking a generous interpretation of the category, the number of posts with sociopolitical consciousness remained low.

As shown in Figure 7, the 'portfolio' category significantly outweighs the others. Together with the 'skill-share/freelancing offer' category, the distribution suggests that these platforms are primarily used for self-promotion and professional visibility, with substantially less emphasis on sociopolitical commentary. Instagram is a primary platform for sharing portfolios, skills, or promotions. Apart from highlighting the minimal presence of sociopolitical awareness across platforms, the categorisation sheds light on how the term 'digital fashion' is currently perceived within social media, as outlined in the introduction.

Limitations

The research methodology had several limits. Firstly, the AI platform could not access closed communities like private Facebook groups or Discord servers.

Secondly, keyword-based searches often returned irrelevant content due to the term 'digital' having wide-ranging meanings. The popularity of the topic also causes the hashtag to appear in unrelated posts, especially those promoting competitions and celebrity gossip. The hashtag also often appears in deceptive posts featuring AI-generated models, directing users to adult sites, as recently reported in mainstream media (See Nguyen and Workman 2024). Lastly, the platform's sentiment analysis function proved unreliable and was thus excluded from this study. AI-driven tools struggle to capture the complexities of human language and imagery, leading to a high margin of error in classifying posts as positive, negative, or neutral (Figure 8).

Such limitations highlight how AI-powered social listening platforms, while efficient at processing large volumes of data, can potentially skew research through their technical—and 'emotional'—constraints. Frequent manual filtering remains essential, though such oversight demands significant time, offsetting the efficiency gained through automation. This reflects broader discussions about AI-human collaboration in fashion industries, where concerns about job displacement coexist with discussions for improving efficiency: for example, within digital fashion where digital- and AI-fluency increasingly complements traditional creative skills.

Fig. 8. An example of inconsistent AI- powered sentiment analysis.

CONCLUSION

This article has traced the historical roots of digital fashion’s self-proclaimed radical stance, revealing how digital utopianism—alongside participatory and non-hierarchical approaches within art, design, and media—has shaped its ideological positioning. The examination of Web3’s ideology, rooted in the radical politics and alternative cultures of the San Francisco Bay Area, has highlighted three main influences on digital fashion’s values: environmental sustainability, decentralisation, and digital accountability. However, the AI social listening analysis has revealed a significant gap between digital fashion’s purported revolutionary aspirations and its actual state. Returning to the concept

of 'fashion public' introduced above, these shortcomings suggest that digital fashion spaces have yet to meet the conditions for the public sphere. Evidence of sociopolitical deliberation through discourse and practice is notably scarce: prevailing attitudes on social media tend to reinforce existing fashion hierarchies and consumerist frameworks rather than challenge them. The manual monitoring of Pulsar data reveals that critical engagement with digital fashion primarily stems from established industry leaders and those in adjacent disciplines such as gaming and software development, rather than grassroots movements. It appears that the ideological statements discussed in the introduction are shaped by early adopters of Web3 technologies. Journalists who echo similar narratives in other fields also contribute to this framing.

As Fred Turner (2017) contends, the issue with technological utopianism lies not in the technological aspect, but in the utopian element, which assumes a totalising perspective. Technology can 'promote authoritarianism as well as liberty, scarcity as well as abundance, the extension as well as the abolition of toil' (Marcuse [1941] 1998: 41). Discussion on digital fashion demands neither absolute faith nor pessimism, but rather careful deliberation about the kinds of practices and relations that can emerge from the boundaries between physical and digital realms. Instead of totalising rhetoric, the fashion public can engage constructively with the existing system, debating effective policies and promoting education among creators and consumers to develop critical thinking.

Despite often being dismissed as lacking depth, fashion's ubiquity in everyday life means it both shapes and reflects the world. Adapting Arjun Appadurai's (1996: 4, 8) analysis of mass media, fashion can be seen as a pervasive cultural force that compels collective imagination, nurturing a group that imagines and feels together. The core question here is whether fashion can critically engage with social issues while operating within market economies. T.V. Reed (2014: 134) notes that even the most defiant art object can be subdued through 'aesthetic neutralisation'. Similarly, the materiality of fashion can dilute its political potency: the fashion system has consistently 'fashionalised' anti-fashion or countercultural objects. This process of commodifying tangible countercultural expressions highlights the potential of dematerialised digital fashion as an oppositional space, one where critical voices might be preserved

and amplified. Fashion in extended reality can position itself as a form of radical media where political, ethical, and aesthetic dimensions intersect—what Félix Guattari (1995: 134) describes as 'transversal junctions'—to provoke change.

In addition, the convergence of the physical and digital, as well as the radical and the commercial, can be strategically exploited, opening space for subversion from within the system. For instance, fashion holds a distinctive advantage as a dynamic that thrives in urban environments and many fashion retail spaces incorporate the functions of cafés, galleries, and/or libraries. These spaces should serve a dual purpose—as retail settings and as venues for the public to engage in critical discussions and lifelong education. Such pedagogic potential of fashion retail spaces would be enhanced by integrating digital elements. Digital fashion, while lacking physical serendipity and spontaneity, can expand such public sphere creatively and geographically. Since 2020, there has been a shift in consumer behaviour, with an increasing emphasis placed on the sociopolitical positioning of fashion brands (Huggard et al. 2023: 555-556). This shift has yet to emerge in the digital fashion spaces on social media, where immense political potential lies. This potential resides in critical fashion publics using these platforms to express their values and influence the direction and behaviour of the fashion industry.

This article makes several contributions to academic discourse. The combination of historical analysis with AI social listening offers a novel methodological approach to studying digital culture. By analysing digital fashion's radicalism as rooted in historical digital utopianisms and counterculture, this study exposes how it recycles historical narratives without acknowledging their limitations. Connecting fashion studies with technology and political theory, the work systematically challenges digital fashion's revolutionary claims whilst advocating constructive alternatives for genuine transformation. Further inquiry should explore specific ways to enhance fashion's criticality within the market economy, ensuring that its potential as a site of social and critical engagement is fully realised whilst maintaining its accessibility to diverse communities.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The author thanks the editors and anonymous peer reviewers for their constructive feedback and guidance in improving this article.

This work was supported by the British Academy's Talent Development Awards Scheme 2023–24 (Grant No. TDA23\230206) funded by the Department for Science, Innovation and Technology (DSIT). The author (co-investigator) is grateful for this financial support which made this research possible.

NOTES

1. Extended reality (XR) encompasses three main categories: virtual reality (VR), augmented reality (AR), and mixed reality (MR). VR fully immerses users in computer-generated environments. AR overlays digital elements onto the physical world, popularly known as 'phygital'. MR combines elements of both VR and AR.
2. Dionisio et al. (2013: 6-7) note that Neal Stephenson coined the term 'metaverse' in his 1992 science fiction *Snow Crash*. Other scholarly descriptions include 'a network of digitally mediated spaces that immerse users in shared, real-time experiences' (Hadi et al. 2024: 143) and 'a projected expansion and networking of virtual reality technologies online' (Hawes 2023: 18).
3. For example, McDowell (2024) reports that a beauty brand 'found a way to bring the metaverse into the real world: visitors could stand in front of a mirror to digitally try on lipstick, then take home a printed image of their look'.
4. Digital fashion gained momentum in 2019 with the AR dress 'Iridescence' by The Fabricant being sold for \$9,500 at the Ethereum Summit auction in New York. The COVID-19 pandemic significantly accelerated the industry's digital transformation, with fashion weeks in Shanghai, Moscow, and Helsinki shifting to virtual formats in 2020. Luxury fashion have since embraced XR spaces, with many brands creating digital products authenticated by NFTs and establishing gaming collaborations.

5. 'Web3' refers to a proposed decentralised version of the internet. It is generally understood as a collection of technologies, including blockchain, cryptocurrencies, non-fungible tokens (NFTs), and distributed autonomous organizations (DAOs) (Hawes 2023: 6; Murray et al. 2023). While the term was first used in 2014, it only gained traction in 2021 (Hawes 2023: 11-12).
6. In this study, 'sociopolitical consciousness' is defined as awareness of and engagement with liberal values that extend beyond commercial or aesthetic foci. It includes equitable access and participation (individual rights, diversity, inclusivity, equal opportunity, decentralisation, collaboration), sustainability (cultural, social, economic, environmental), and accountability (transparency, privacy, intellectual property, supply chain integrity). This definition reflects contemporary pedagogical approaches in contextual studies within UK fashion courses, which emphasise critical thinking and deliberation on responsible practice. It is also informed by insights from the Pulsar platform search, as detailed in the methodology section.
7. Langdon Winner (1997a; 1997b: 14-15) uses the term 'cyberlibertarianism', criticising it as a form of radical right-wing libertarian thought. Thomas Malaby (2009: 16), in his study of software company Linden Lab, describes the employees' attitude as 'technoliberalism', marked by a distrust of authority and a strong faith in technology.
8. The *Whole Earth Catalog* (1968-72), established by Stewart Brand, has had an outsized influence on the understandings of digital technology through its vision of countercultural living and peer-to-peer networking. Its mix of product recommendations, DIY resources, and books—including Wiener's (1948) *Cybernetics*—reflected the collaborative, user-driven approach that would define the web. (Wiener 2018; Turner 2013: 47)
9. Catherine Mason (2018) defines computer art as 'work made with or through the agency of a digital computer predominately as a tool[,] material, method or concept, from around the late-1950s onward'.
10. Computer-generated imagery (CGI) in films, digital fashion, and gaming share core 3D technologies. Digital fashion uses tools such as CLO3D or Marvelous Designer to simulate authentic clothing and models; gaming and

film CGI have exchanged innovations, talent, and visual influences for decades. See Harris (2013) for an early exploration of the connection.

11. Following Wardle and Derakhshan's (2017) categorisation, 'mis-information' refers to false information that is shared unintentionally, without the intent to deceive; 'dis-information' refers to false information that is intentionally shared to deceive and cause harm; 'mal-information' refers to true information that is shared with the intent to cause harm, such as by exposing someone's private details.
12. For example, events such as the 1989 Tiananmen Square protests, the Hong Kong protests, Covid lockdown dissent, treatment of Muslims, and discussions of Tibet and Taiwan's independence. (Scharre 2023; The Economist 2025)
13. Oxford Reference (2011) defines 'dataveillance' as 'monitoring or profiling a person through their personal data records, rather than by listening to or viewing their activities'.
14. Without daily filtering, the Pulsar dataset became inundated with bikini-clad AI-generated models with exaggerated features, likely driven by algorithmic biases thriving in the attention economy.
15. For example, a virtual bag by Gucci was sold for \$4,115 on Roblox, exceeding the value of its physical counterpart. (Palumbo 2022; Wootton and Bronstein 2023: 21)
16. Although Ethereum's 2022 switch to a Proof-of-Stake model reduced energy consumption, these changes reintroduced intermediaries and hierarchies, undermining Web3's promise of decentralised control. (Bindseil and Schaaf 2022; Hawes 2023: 24; Stackpole 2022)
17. The Boolean search query—"digital fashion") AND NOT ([...])—was then adapted for platform-specific queries.
18. The Boolean search query was "digital fashion" AND (subculture OR "sustainab"* OR "collaborat"* OR "customiz"* OR "democrati"* OR "subvert"* OR "politic"* OR "decentralis" OR "dematerialis"* OR "participat"* OR "ethic"* OR "disrupt"* OR revolution.

REFERENCES

- Appadurai A (1996) *Modernity at Large*. Minnesota, MN: University of Minnesota Press.
- Bain M (2023) Digital fashion's unlikely alliance. *The Business of Fashion*, 17 May. <https://www.businessoffashion.com/articles/technology/digital-fashions-unlikely-alliance/> (accessed 18 October 2023).
- Barbrook R and Cameron A (1995) The Californian ideology. *Science as Culture* 6 (1): 44-72.
- Beer D and Burrows R (2010) Consumption, prosumption and participatory web cultures. *Journal of Consumer Culture* 10 (1): 3-12.
- Bindseil U and Schaaf J (2022) Bitcoin's last stand. *European Central Bank*. <https://www.ecb.europa.eu/press/blog/date/2022/html/ecb.blog221130~5301eed19.en.html> (accessed 2 January 2025).
- Black S (2019) Sustainability and digitalization. In: Geczy A and Karaminas V (eds) *The End of Fashion*, 113-132. London: Bloomsbury.
- Blackman R (2022) Why blockchain's ethical stakes are so high. *Harvard Business Review*, 10 May. <https://hbr.org/2022/05/why-blockchains-ethical-stakes-are-so-high> (accessed 7 December 2024).
- Bonsaver L (2025) Can Beijing capture the hearts of Taiwan's teenagers? *Observer Research Foundation*, 24 March. <https://www.orfonline.org/expert-speak/can-beijing-capture-the-hearts-of-taiwan-s-teenagers> (accessed 7 April 2025).
- The British Academy (2024) Code of Practice. <https://www.thebritishacademy.ac.uk/funding/code-practice/> (accessed 22 November 2024).
- Buderi R (1996) *The Invention that Changed the World*. New York: Simon & Schuster.
- Castells M (2001) *The Internet Galaxy*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- CLO Virtual Fashion (2023) CLO Virtual Fashion and Epic Games together invest in the future of digital fashion. *PRNewswire*, 11 May. <https://www.prnewswire.com/news-releases/clo-virtual-fashion-and-epic-games-together-invest-in-the-future-of-digital-fashion-301822013.html> (accessed 18 October 2023)
- van Dijck J and Nieborg D (2009) Wikinomics and its discontents. *New Media & Society* 11 (4): 855-874.
- Dionisio JDN et al. (2013) 3D virtual worlds and the metaverse. *ACM Computing Surveys* 45 (3): Article 34.

- The Economist (2024) Autocracies are exporting autocracy to their diasporas. *The Economist*, 29 February. <https://www-economist-com/leaders/2024/02/29/autocracies-are-exporting-autocracy-to-their-diasporas> (accessed 1 March 2024).
- The Economist (2025) A protest against America's TikTok ban is mired in contradiction. *The Economist*, 17 January. <https://www.economist.com/united-states/2025/01/17/a-protest-against-americas-tiktok-ban-is-mired-in-contradiction> (accessed 18 Jan 2025).
- The Fabricant (2022) How to be punk in web3. *Medium*, 25 October. <https://thefabricant.medium.com/how-to-be-punk-in-web3-f09cd1e663fc> (accessed 3 November 2024).
- The Fabricant (2024) Where the computer ends, you continue. *Medium*, 18 April. <https://thefabricant.medium.com/where-the-computer-ends-you-continue-2baa34954200> (accessed 3 November 2024).
- Foster JB and McChesney RW (2014) Surveillance capitalism. *Monthly Review*, 1 July. <https://monthlyreview.org/2014/07/01/surveillance-capitalism/> (accessed 17 January 2018).
- Friedman V and Bromwich JE (2018) Cambridge Analytica used fashion tastes to identify right-wing voters. *The New York Times*, 29 November. <https://www.nytimes.com/2018/11/29/style/cambridge-analytica-fashion-data.html> (accessed 4 February 2019).
- Graham-Harrison E and Lin CH (2023) 'Into brain and the heart': how China is using apps to woo Taiwan's teenagers. *The Guardian*, 13 August. <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2023/aug/13/into-brain-and-the-heart-how-china-is-using-apps-to-woo-taiwans-teenagers> (accessed 13 August 2023).
- Guattari F (1995) *Chaosmosis*. Bloomington, IN: Indiana University Press.
- Habermas J ([1962] 1991) *The Structural Transformation of the Public Sphere*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.
- Hadi R et al. (2024) The metaverse: A new digital frontier for consumer behavior. *Journal of Consumer Psychology* 34 (1): 142-166.
- Harris J (2013) Digital skin. *Textile* 11 (3): 242-261
- Hawes B (2023) Web3: The promise & the reality. *WST and WSI White Paper*. University of Southampton.
- Heneage G (2023) The influencers' new clothes. *The Times*, 19 April. <https://www.thetimes.com/uk/social-media/article/digital-fashion-buyers-influencers-instagram-clothes-873zk5v8t> (accessed 19 April 2023).

- Highhouse CH (2022) China content on TikTok. *Online Media and Global Communication* 1 (4): 697-722.
- Hille K (2025) Is TikTok pushing Taiwan's young people closer to China? *The Financial Times*, 17 January. <https://www.ft.com/content/e25ee12b-3a4a-4a15-bd5e-0f5fb410e856> (accessed 19 January 2025).
- Huggard E et al. (2023) New luxury ideologies. *Fashion Theory* 27 (4): 555-579.
- Jenkins H (2014) Rethinking 'rethinking convergence/culture'. *Cultural Studies* 28 (2): 267-297
- Karp R et al. (2024) How your business should tap into the creator economy. *Harvard Business Review*, 22 May. <https://hbr.org/2024/05/how-your-business-should-tap-into-the-creator-economy> (accessed 24 May 2024).
- Knibbs K (2024) AI slop is flooding *Medium*. *WIRED*, 28 October. <https://www.wired.com/story/ai-generated-medium-posts-content-moderation/> (accessed 8 November 2024).
- Kozinets RV (2022) Immersive netnography. *Journal of Service Management* 34 (1): 100-125 .
- Kücklich J (2005) Precarious playbour. *The Fibreculture Journal* (5). <https://five.fibreculturejournal.org/fcj-025-precariou-playbour-modders-and-the-digital-games-industry/> (accessed 18 November 2024).
- Langley P and Leyshon A (2017) Platform capitalism. *Finance and Society* 3 (1): 11-31.
- Lee YS (2024) From passivity to agency: audience participation in fashion shows. *Bloomsbury Fashion Central*. London: Bloomsbury. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5040/9781350881419.001>.
- Leroux-Parra M (2020) Esports part 1. *Harvard International Review*, 24 April. <https://hir.harvard.edu/esports-part-1-what-are-esports/> (accessed 3 August 2022).
- Livingstone S and Lunt P (1994) The mass media, democracy and the public sphere. In: Livingstone S and Lunt P (eds) *Talk on Television Audience Participation and Public Debate*, 9-35. London: Routledge.
- Lovink G and Tkacz N (2015) MoneyLab: sprouting new digital-economic forms. In: Lovink G et al. (eds) *MoneyLab Reader*. Amsterdam: Institute of Network Cultures.
- Lu D (2025) We tried out DeepSeek. *The Guardian* 28 January. <https://www.theguardian.com/technology/2025/jan/28/we-tried-out->

- deepseek-it-works-well-until-we-asked-it-about-tiananmen-square-and-taiwan (accessed 28 January 2025).
- Marcuse H ([1941] 1998) Some social implications of modern technology. In: Kellner D (ed.) *Technology, War, and Fascism*, 41–65. London: Routledge.
- Malaby T (2009) *Making Virtual Worlds*. Ithaca, NY: Cornell University Press.
- Marwick A (2012) The public domain: Surveillance in everyday life. *Surveillance & Society* 9 (4): 378-393.
- Mason C (2018) Cybernetic Serendipity. *Studio International*, 11 March. <https://www.studiointernational.com/index.php/cybernetic-serendipity-history-and-lasting-legacy> (accessed 13 July 2018).
- McDowell M (2024) Why the metaverse is moving into physical retail. *Vogue Business*, 5 November. <https://www.voguebusiness.com/story/technology/why-the-metaverse-is-moving-into-physical-retail> (accessed 6 November 2024).
- Metaverse Fashion Council (2024) My aesthetics is the culmination of humanity's inevitable obsolescence. <https://metaversefashioncouncil.org/tpost/ftbnhb7141-my-aesthetics-is-the-culmination-of-huma> (accessed 21 November 2024).
- Moore E (2024) Man vs machinima. *The Financial Times*, 2 November. <https://www.ft.com/content/8dac8aac-d255-48e9-9172-0b0cc45b3c5e> (accessed 2 November 2024).
- Murray A et al. (2023) The promise of a decentralized internet. *Business Horizons* 66 (2): 191-202.
- Natale S and Ballatore A (2014) 'The web will kill them all': New media, digital utopia, and political struggle in the Italian 5-Star Movement. *Media, Culture & Society* 36 (1): 105-121.
- Nguyen K and Workman M (2024) 'AI pimps' and their fake influencers are mass-harvesting women's videos to peddle porn. *ABC News* 13 April. <https://www.abc.net.au/news/2024-04-14/how-ai-pimps-influencers-are-using-womens-videos/103658046> (accessed 3 November 2024).
- Orton-Johnson K (2024) *Digital Culture and Society*. London: Sage.
- Oxford Reference (2011) Dataveillance. In: Chandler D and Munday R (eds) *A Dictionary of Media and Communication*. Oxford: Oxford University Press. <https://www.oxfordreference.com/view/10.1093/oi/authority.20110803095701590> (accessed 4 Feb 2025).

- Palmer A (2024) Pulsar Group security, privacy and compliance overview. *Pulsar Group*. <https://www.pulsargroup.com/trustcentre/> (accessed 21 February 2025).
- Palumbo J (2022) You can thank The Sims for the rise of luxury fashion in gaming. *CNN*, 22 November. <https://edition.cnn.com/style/article/digital-fashion-video-games-the-sims/index.html> (accessed 17 February 2024).
- Peres R et al. (2024) The creator economy. *International Journal of Research in Marketing* 41 (3): 403-410.
- Pescott C (2023) How beauty filters like TikTok's 'bold glamour' affect tweens using social media. *The Conversation*, 14 April. <https://theconversation.com/how-beauty-filters-like-tiktoks-bold-glamour-affect-tweens-using-social-media-203383> (accessed 1 November 2024).
- Pfister DS (2018) Public Sphere(s), publics, and counterpublics. *Oxford Research Encyclopedia of Communication*, 26 September. <https://oxfordre.com/communication/view/10.1093/acrefore/9780190228613.001.0001/acrefore-9780190228613-e-562> (accessed 14 February 2025).
- Pfister DS and Yang M (2018) Five theses on technoliberalism and the networked public sphere. *Communication and the Public* 3 (3): 247-262.
- Raymond ES (1999) *The Cathedral and the Bazaar*. Sebastopol, CA: O'Reilly & Associates.
- Reed TV (2014) Roundtable. In: Flood C and Grindon G (eds) *Disobedient Objects*, 130–135. London: V&A Publishing.
- Reed TV (2018) *Digitized Lives*. London and New York: Routledge.
- Richardson S (2025) The media show. *BBC Radio 4*. 29 January. <https://www.bbc.co.uk/sounds/play/m0027cv6> (accessed 30 January 2025).
- Ritzer G and Jurgenson N (2010) Production, consumption, prosumption. *Journal of Consumer Culture* 10 (1): 13-36.
- Rolf S and Schindler S (2023) The US–China rivalry and the emergence of state platform capitalism. *Environment and Planning A* 55 (5): 1255-1280.
- Rose S (2022) How *Tron* changed cinema. *The Guardian*, 5 July. <https://www.theguardian.com/film/2022/jul/05/tron-steven-lisberger-interview> (accessed 21 December 2024).
- Särmäkari N and Vänskä A (2022) Fashion 4.0 designers as cyborgs, experimenting and designing with generative algorithms. *International Journal of Fashion Design, Technology and Education* 15 (2): 211-220.
- Rosen S (1969) Electronic computers: A historical survey. *ACM Computing Surveys* 1 (1): 7-36.

- Scharre P (2023) The dangers of the global spread of China's digital authoritarianism. *Center for a New American Security*, 4 May. <https://www.cnas.org/publications/congressional-testimony/the-dangers-of-the-global-spread-of-chinas-digital-authoritarianism>.
- Scott L and Armstrong R (2024) How modelling agent Chelsea Bonner is taking on artificial intelligence to avoid 'cataclysmic step backwards' for industry. *ABC News*, 5 May. <https://www.abc.net.au/news/2024-05-06/chelsea-bonner-fight-against-ai-models/103769766> (accessed 3 November 2024).
- Srnicek N (2017) *Platform Capitalism*. Cambridge: Polity Press.
- Stackpole T (2022) Cautionary tales from cryptoland. *Harvard Business Review*, 10 May. <https://hbr.org/2022/05/cautionary-tales-from-cryptoland> (accessed 7 December 2024).
- Tan A (2024) David Cash and Antoni Tudisco on the Digital Fashion Designer's Council and the launch of Fashion Week Connect. *Vogue Singapore*, 19 August. <https://vogue.sg/digital-fashion-designers-council-fashion-week-connect/> (accessed 21 August 2024).
- Tepe J and Koohnavard S (2022) Fashion and game design as hybrid practices. *International Journal of Fashion Design, Technology and Education* 16 (1): 37-45
- Terlutter R and Capella ML (2013) The gamification of advertising. *Journal of Advertising* 42 (2-3): 95-112.
- TFL (2022) Apparel, luxury brands lead on list of those embracing NFTs. *The Fashion Law*, 13 October. <https://www.thefashionlaw.com/apparel-and-luxury-brands-lead-on-list-of-industries-embracing-nfts-projects/> (accessed 2 November 2024).
- Toffler A (1980) *The Third Wave*. New York: William Morrow & Company.
- Townsend L and Wallace C (2016) Social media research: A guide to ethics. *University of Aberdeen*. https://www.gla.ac.uk/media/Media_487729_smxx.pdf (accessed 8 November 2024).
- Turner F (2006a) *From Counterculture to Cyberculture*. Chicago, IL: University of Chicago Press.
- Turner F (2006b) How digital technology found utopian ideology. In: Silver D and Massanari A (eds) *Critical Cyberculture Studies*, 255-269. New York University Press.

- Turner F (2013) The politics of the Whole. In: Diederichsen D and Franke A (eds) *The Whole Earth: California and the Disappearance of the Outside*, 43–53. Berlin: Sternberg Press.
- Turner F (2017) Don't be evil: Fred Turner on utopias, frontiers, and programmers. *Logic(s)* (3). <https://logicmag.io/justice/fred-turner-dont-be-evil/> (accessed 2 November 2024).
- Turner F (2023a) Digital utopianism: where do we stand 10 years later? *Sciences Po*, 21 June. <https://www.sciencespo.fr/en/news/digital-utopianism-where-do-we-stand-10-years-later/> (accessed 2 November 2024).
- Turner F (2023b) From counterculture to cyberculture. *Sciences Po*, 16 June. <https://www.youtube.com/live/upBpriCBAzI> (accessed 3 November 2024).
- U.S. Copyright Office (2024) Copyright and artificial intelligence: Digital replicas. July. <https://www.copyright.gov/ai/Copyright-and-Artificial-Intelligence-Part-1-Digital-Replicas-Report.pdf> (accessed 3 August 2024).
- U.S. Copyright Office (2025) Copyright and artificial intelligence: Copyrightability. January. <https://www.copyright.gov/ai/Copyright-and-Artificial-Intelligence-Part-2-Copyrightability-Report.pdf> (accessed 31 January 2024).
- Vincent J (2023) *Medium* welcomes posts written with AI as long they're 'clearly labeled'. *The Verge*, 27 January. <https://www.theverge.com/2023/1/27/23573954/medium-platform-publisher-ai-written-posts-policy-chatgpt> (accessed 29 November 2024).
- Waldrop MM (2001) *The Dream Machine*. New York: Penguin.
- Wardle C and Derakhshan H (2017) Information disorder. *Council of Europe*. <https://edoc.coe.int/en/media/7495-information-disorder-toward-an-interdisciplinary-framework-for-research-and-policy-making.html> (accessed 3 February 2025).
- Watstein SB and Czarnecki K (2010) Virtual worlds, dress, and fashion. In: Eicher JB and Tortora PG (eds) *Berg Encyclopaedia of World Dress and Fashion: Vol. 10*, 276-282. Oxford: Berg
- Wiener A (2018) The complicated legacy of Stewart Brand's 'Whole Earth Catalog'. *The New Yorker*, 16 November. <https://www.newyorker.com/news/letter-from-silicon-valley/the-complicated-legacy-of-stewart-brands-whole-earth-catalog> (accessed 5 January 2025).
- Wiener N (1948) *Cybernetics*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.

- Wilson H (1963) Labour and the scientific revolution. <https://web-archives.univ-pau.fr/english/TD2doc2.pdf> (accessed 12 October 2024).
- Winner L (1997a) Technology today: Utopia or dystopia? *Social Research* 64 (3): 989-1017.
- Winner L (1997b) Cyberlibertarian myths and the prospects for community. *ACM Sigcas Computers and Society* 27 (3): 14-19.
- Wootton C and Bronstein M (2023) 2023 Digital expression, fashion & beauty trends. *Roblox*. <https://corp.roblox.com/newsroom/2023/11/insights-latest-digital-expression-fashion-beauty-trends-report> (accessed 18 November 2024).
- Wu D (2024) Pop and propaganda. *The Initium*, 22 May. <https://worldcrunch.com/culture-society/taiwanese-teens-china-social-media/> (accessed 18 June 2024).
- Zuboff S (2015) Big Other: Surveillance capitalism and the prospects of an information civilization. *Journal of Information Technology* 30: 75-89.